

Outdoor Learning for Learner Identity – A case study exploring the child’s learner identity while experiencing outdoor learning in the Irish primary school context.

A review of Literature

Abstract: This study explores Outdoor Learning (OL) as an approach to teaching the primary school curriculum towards developing learner identities among children. The competencies and skills aligned with Learner Identity (LI) development align with the benefits of OL which demonstrate similar values and meaning such as self-esteem, self-awareness, independence, confidence, relationship skills, motivation to learn and problem-solving skills. The literature presented in this paper will inform an OL program to enhance children’s LI which arguably can be easily integrated with all curriculum areas.

Highlights

- OL is a pedagogical approach to teaching with, in and about the outdoor environment.
- LI is how the child feels about themselves as a learner
- OL provides a good space for LI development because the benefits of OL align with the key competencies needed for LI development.

Key Words: Outdoor Learning, Learner Identity, Primary Curriculum.

Introduction

This paper explores the literature informing a study about children’s sense of LI while experiencing OL in the Irish Primary School context. This paper will present two key themes that inform this study, OL and LI. The paper will firstly introduce OL. Following on from this, international curricula which include elements of OL are reviewed. Then OL in Ireland

is examined. LI is then explored along with ways of developing LI in children. Finally, OL and LI are brought together as a complimentary duo in a concluding paragraph.

Outdoor Learning

This section begins by presenting the history and the philosophical underpinnings of OL. OL and its benefits are explored following with a review of OL in practice and internationally. The barriers of practicing OL are then discussed. The section concludes with examining OL in Ireland. A definition of OL is derived from the literature for the purpose of this study.

History and philosophical underpinnings of Outdoor Learning

We see elements of nature and the importance of the garden in the beliefs of many of the great educational philosophers and theologians such as Comenius, Pestalozzi, Froebel, Dewey, McMillan, Steiner, Montessori (Pound and Hughes, 2005). Comenius directly links his principles of teaching with nature (Thatcher, 1907). He compares the progression in teaching and learning to nature when he states that “nature advances from what is easy to what is more difficult” (Thatcher, 1907). Pestalozzi states that education must be “according to nature” and that all children must have an equal right to education (Pound and Hughes, 2005). Fröbel also saw the importance of the outdoors in the use of the garden and the language he used in his philosophy with the word kindergarten meaning “children’s garden” (Fröbel, 1887). The hands-on aspect of OL is reflected in Dewey’s (1938) learn by doing approach. Dewey’s (1938) belief that education should be based on real life situations links with the real-life experience of being outdoors. Margaret McMillan argued that learning in the outdoors is embedded in action and aimed to improve children’s health and wellbeing. She placed the garden as an integral part of a child’s learning along with time and space. She

set up an open air camp to nurture disadvantaged children with the aim of fostering skills to enable them to take their place in society (Pound and Hughes, 2005).

Defining Outdoor Learning and its Benefits

According to Marchant et al. (2019) OL “is a pedagogical approach used to enrich learning, enhance school engagement and improve pupil health and wellbeing” (p. 1). Similarly, Robertson (2014) describes OL as “an umbrella term which covers every type of learning experience which happens outdoors” (p.2). OL is one of the pillars of Outdoor Education (OE) which came to the fore in the 1960s due to the emergence of Environmental Education (An Taisce, 2021). OE and Outdoor Adventure Education (OAE) focus on outdoor adventure, challenge and skills (Smith and Walsh, 2019). While OL encompasses these, it goes beyond this to include discovery, experimentation (Meighan and Rubenstein, 2018), learning about and connecting to the natural world, and engaging in environmental and adventure activities (Learning and Teaching Scotland *et al.*, 2010). OL also involves the transformation of knowledge, skills, attitudes and behaviours through direct engagement with the outdoor environment for the personal and social benefit of individuals, families, society and the planet (Natural England, 2016; Fiennes *et al.*, 2015).

The benefits of OL are evidenced, acknowledged and accepted (Lambert et al., 2020). Bringing learning beyond the physical landscape of the classroom and into the outdoors provides children with freedom in learning, as the open environment offers space for children to think using all their senses (Harris, 2018). This freedom in OL benefits all learners as it supports children of all abilities in reaching learning outcomes (Marchant *et al.*, 2019). Experiencing OL can have a positive impact on children’s self-confidence, self-esteem and self-control (Barron, 2014) as they learn alongside their classmates in a relaxed, therapeutic

outdoor environment. In addition, we see OL improving children's social and communication skills (Barfod *et al.*, 2016) as they learn together in a different physical and social environment. Other competencies that link with OL include; being creative (McAnally, Robertson and Hancox, 2018), being mathematical (Keith, 2017) and being an active citizen (Braun and Dierkes, 2017).

Outdoor Learning in Practice

It is important to note that OL is not a replacement for learning that happens inside the classroom but an extension to that learning by creating a seamless link between the indoor and outdoor classrooms. Once learning is moved beyond the classroom walls, the quality of the outdoor space is not important, what matters is that "the quality of the experience is the best it can be and is authentic, meaningful and relevant for the children involved" (Robertson, 2014, p.2). A forest or a specifically designed outdoor space is not necessary, but simply moving outside is all it takes in making OL accessible to all schools. Although, just like indoor lessons, OL lessons must be effectively planned, taught and reflected upon to ensure quality learning is taking place (Benefield, 2006).

The wide variety of OL lessons and programs makes it difficult to list clear characteristics of OL for schools (Meighan and Rubenstein, 2018). In their synthesis of literature surrounding OL in schools, Meighan and Rubenstein (2018) do not mention characteristics of OL and state that the majority of literature available focuses on the outputs of OL programmes, finishing with a call for more research to be conducted on the inputs or characteristics of successful OL programmes. From this synthesis of literature, Meighan and Rubenstein (2018) call on educators to expose children to the outdoors regularly, explore the outdoors with all the senses, create experiences that provide context and application of material presented, and

provide pre- and post-activities to reinforce gains made while OL. Meighan and Rubenstein (2018) list the factors influencing the use of OL programmes in schools as being financially self-sufficient, an outdoor space physically isolated from the school, teachers visibly active in the school, outdoor spaces supported and sponsored by the local community and other organisations. With the growth of interest in OL in the last few years (Waite, 2020), it is important for researchers to begin to refine definitions, characteristics and key elements of OL to ensure quality teaching and learning.

Outdoor Learning Internationally

A greater understanding of OL in schools can be gained by examining how other countries around the world have incorporated the outdoors into their curricula and frameworks. Countries such as Norway, New Zealand and Canada, are renowned for their engagement with the outdoors. However, in schools, OL is not prominent across all subjects. In Norway, a country who follows the 'friluftsliv' (*outdoor life*) way of life, 81.9% of its teachers participate in outdoor activities on a regular basis (Aadland et al., 2009) and it is likely that OL is occurring in the lives of young children both in school and outside school. Therefore, it may be sufficient that they are only specifically teaching outdoor skills through Physical Education (PE).

New Zealand added OL? as one of seven key elements in the health and PE curriculum in 1999 (Ministry of Education, 1999). Whereas in Canada, we see provinces offering OE as an elective subject in PE in high school for personal and social development, fundamental core skills, environmental awareness and sustainability and wellness. The OE curriculum for New Brunswick gives clear curricular aims and outcomes along with assessment templates. Within this curriculum links to external websites, handbooks and

resources are provided to assist teachers with the implementation (Government of New Brunswick, 2014). This supportive approach to curriculum design may encourage teachers to effectively teach OE. Gillis (2016) found this to be a success in schools with the addition of an assigned Outdoor Educator on site who supported teachers and helped develop curriculum resources. Without preservice training in OL, these toolkits and continuous professional development may be beneficial for teachers to successfully implement any curricular advancements and progression.

In 2004 Scotland launched the 'Curriculum for Excellence' (Learning and Teaching Scotland et al., 2010) through OL. This curriculum recognises and supports the principle that OL exists in all curricular areas. It was created to assist educators in providing quality OL experiences. Teaching using this pedagogical model has been going from strength to strength in recent years (Beames, Nicol and Higgins, 2012). Beames et al. (2012) created a practical guide for OL with ideas and support for teachers and practitioners in Scotland. Instead of OL being limited to PE like in Norway and New Zealand, Scotland has adopted OL as an underlying concept within all curricular areas, resulting in more regular and relevant OL opportunities taking place. However, we are yet to understand how this curricular change is being implemented on the ground in Scottish schools and to what extent.

Perhaps it is not curricular change that will change a teaching method, but professional development of those already teaching and ensuring that pre-service teachers experience OL during their pre-service training. Although these countries are leading and developing further in the areas of OL, they too experience obstacles and difficulties making curricular aims and outcomes a reality in schools. OL is not straightforward but effort in making it happen is necessary.

Obstacles in providing OL

It is important to note that individual teachers perceive different risks and challenges when teaching in natural areas and report obstacles such as transportation, teacher ability, funding, state testing, planning time, safety/liability and access. (Meighan and Rubenstein, 2018).

Despite Norway's teachers having a lot of experience in personal outdoor pursuits, 64.4% of them said that they required extra training in friluftsliv for school (Aadland et al., 2009). Like Norway, a study conducted in 2002 and 2003 around the teaching of OE in New Zealand found it to differ nationwide. It emerged that there were multiple ways in which OE was understood, thus leading to discrepancy in teaching it (Zink and Boyes, 2006). Again, despite the advancements of adding OE to the curriculum in a country where regular engagement with the outdoors is the norm, issues arise around facilitating this curricular change. Cost of programme implementation, crowded curricular demands, paperwork involved in organising OE, demands on personal time, staffing relief, lack of suitable venues for teaching OE and inflexible timetables all featured as barriers for New Zealand's teachers (Zink and Boyes, 2006). More recently, Waite (2020) surveyed international expert commentators on OL, which revealed that Scotland still sees primary and secondary school OL implementation fall well below that in early years education. On closer inspection, despite the arrival of the Curriculum of Excellence, teacher training programmes in Scotland do not feature an OL module (*BA Primary Education | Teacher Training Degree | University of Strathclyde*, no date), meaning newly qualified teachers leave university with no experience of providing OL. In Ireland it has been reported that the lack of OL occurring is due to the cultural resistance among teachers (Waite, 2020).

OL in Ireland

Similar to Canada, New Zealand and Norway, children in Ireland experience learning outdoors mainly through the PE programme. However, this does not happen to a large extent (Woods et al. 2018). Outdoor and adventure activities (O&AA) is a strand on the Irish primary PE curriculum. In the Irish primary school curriculum, the strand includes the following strand units; Walking, cycling and camping activities, Orienteering, Outdoor challenges, Water-based activities and Understanding and Appreciation of Outdoor and Adventure Activities (DES, 1999). O&AA has a prominent role in both early years' and post primary education in Ireland with Aistear (NCCA, 2015) listing well-being, identity and belonging, communicating, exploring and thinking as their key themes and the post primary PE curriculum stating that "adventure activities at junior cycle provide students with the opportunity to develop personally, socially, and physically in a safe and challenging environment." (DES, 2003, p.17). Other areas of the primary curriculum encourage the use of outdoors in teaching subjects such as geography and science in which the exploration of the local natural and physical environment is noted as an objective (DES, 1999). For students to experience regular OL it must become a foundational part of the curriculum that features across all curricular subjects.

In recent years Forest Schools have become more popular in Ireland with a total of 43 schools mapped across the country (Map of Forest Schools, 2018). Forest Schools are providing children with experiences learning outdoors. Forest School "is an opportunity for the same group of learners and leaders to spend a sustained period outdoors, once a week, in a wooded environment, ideally year round" (IFSA, 2021). Forest School in Ireland has successfully promoted social and emotional skills through its practice (Murphy, 2018).

However, forest schools are totally independent from and not supported by the Department of Education and Skills in Ireland.

Taking the various definitions, benefits, and barriers of OL into consideration, for the purpose of this study OL is defined as a pedagogical approach to learning with, in and about the outdoor environment.

Learner Identity

Identity is a legal concept established from birth (UN, 1989). Personal identity refers to the way children feel about themselves in comparison to others, their sense of uniqueness and individuality (Brooker & Woodhead, 2008). The development of identity is a never ending process that is constantly under construction throughout a person's entire life (Dewey and Turfs, 1932, Ahn, 2011). However the vital groundwork of identity construction is laid in the early years and this foundation is built upon throughout our lives (Ahn, 2011).

According to Lawson (2014) “ a ‘learner identity’ can be broadly defined as how an individual feels about himself/herself as a learner and the extent to which he/she describes himself/herself as a ‘learner’” (p.343). The Centre for Learner Identity Studies (CLIS) suggests that socio-cultural aspects of individuals' experiences such as gender, generation, place, social class, ethnicity and spirituality/religion are the bases that affect one's experience of being a learner (CLIS, 2014). Falsafi (2010) disagrees with this and uses Bernstein and Solomon's (1999, p. 272) definition as the starting point for defining LI: ‘... resources for constructing belonging, recognition of self and others, and context management (what I am, where, with whom and when)’. This definition and understanding of LI is suited to the context of primary school as these are elements the school can assist the pupils in gaining greater understanding. CLIS's definition may be a fair statement of LI in the broader sense

and since most research around LI is focused on teenagers and adults, this might be an effective way to define it. However, for primary school pupils and their LI, the who, what, with whom, when and why of LI is an effective way to define it, it is accessible for children to understand and grasp, and accessible for teacher assessment and observation. Children must understand what LI is to be able to communicate their LI.

There are numerous views on how a child develops their personal identity. Schaffer (2006) states that identities are acquired and constructed in different ways in different societies and that there is unlikely to be a universal model for this process. However, a common theme within personal identity development is that this occurs in young children (Ahn, 2011). Therefore, early childhood education and primary school are the optimum time for personal identity development (Warin, 2010). Most research on LI focuses on secondary school students, university students and teachers themselves. The dearth of research on primary children's LI is perplexing given that having ownership and understanding of one's own learning and who they see themselves as a learner is an element of many curricula worldwide as they strive to develop the child holistically (NCCA, 1999). This may be because LI is currently overshadowed by identity research in areas of interest such as gender and ethnic belonging (Falsafi, 2010).

Significant LI variables include; perceived learning capability, self-regard, preparedness for learning and learner confidence. These variables are fostered when children are supported in their learning, able to cope with challenges, are cared for, helped and establish friendships through learning (Singal and Swann, 2011). According to CASEL (Bridgeland et al., 2013), competencies and skills associated with identity development include; self-awareness,

self-management, social awareness, relationship skills, responsible decision making, motivation.

Learner Identity Development

In order to understand the phenomena of identity development, and with the idea that identity is developed during childhood, we must look at what supports identity development in the learning context (Collett, 2020). According to Collett, (2020) and Nasir & Cooks (2009) there are three common elements in learning which support the development of identity. Firstly, the physical environment in which learning takes place provides scope for identity development as over time the individual becomes more comfortable and familiar with the environment, promoting further identity development as their ideas, perceptions and relationship with others and the material objects in the environment advances (Nasir and Cooks, 2009; Collett, 2020). Secondly, one's position across a variety of interactions proves to be important when developing identity as the learner experiences and responds to a different status within the group learning dynamic (Nasir and Cooks, 2009; Collett, 2020). One's "positive relationship with others in the context can increase connection to the practice" (Nasir and Cooks, 2009, p. 47). Finally, one's self and relationship with the learning context proves to be important in developing identity in the way that the learner takes ownership or initiative over their own learning (Nasir and Cooks, 2009; Collett, 2020). Offering children an alternative learning context will provide them with another context to connect with and offer more opportunities for self-connection. Something that Nasir & Cooks (2009) fail to mention is the importance of time and space for reflection after learning has taken place (O'Connor, 2019; Collett, 2020). After the learning, the learner reflects on the environment, the relationships and interactions during the learning and the decisions they

made during learning. Leaving time for reflection after learning is a common element of all curricular subjects and is frequently mentioned in research surrounding OAE and OE, components of PE which occur in the outdoor environment (Dismore and Bailey, 2005; Williams and Wainwright, 2016). The three resources outlined by Nasir & Cooks (2009) can also be transferred to primary school and OL where we see the importance of a good learning environment and strong relationships with peers and self.

Learning in the unique context of the outdoor environment can develop skills such as self-esteem, self-awareness, independence, confidence, relationship skills, motivation to learn and problem-solving skills. These are the key skills and competencies needed for LI development (Bridgeland et al., 2013).

Conclusion: Outdoor Learning and Learner Identity – A Complementary Duo

While the research in the previous sections have shown the importance of OL and the impact it may have on LI, there is an alignment or crossover between the two. This section develops this further. Focusing on Bernstein and Solomon's (1999) definition of LI; what I am, where, with whom and when, many links can be made between OL and LI that suggest that OL may be an avenue for development of LI in primary school children.

Firstly, the 'What am I' as a learner comes as children are given control and ownership over their learning (Bernstein and Solomon, 1999). For this to happen they must be given choice and have responsibility over their learning which, over time, will lead to a growth in confidence around the learning and the learning environment which is a key factor of OL (Waite, 2011). Enabling children to cope with challenges in effective ways is also proven to strengthen elements of children's LI such as independence, self-understanding, interpersonal skills, perseverance, leadership, self-confidence and responsible decision making (Orson,

McGovern and Larson, 2020). The ‘what am I’ is also constructed from being supported and cared for during learning (Bernstein and Solomon, 1999). The ‘what am I’ constructs of responsibility, choice, challenge, and care are skills and competencies supported and promoted in OL.

The ‘where’ of Bernstein and Solomon’s (1999) definition can be successfully linked to OL. One’s relationship with the learning context is important in providing a connection with the place (Nasir and Cooks, 2009). The change of learning environment that OL provides allows children to expand their learning environment and offers opportunities to connect or create an association with the outdoors for learning.

The ‘with whom’ signifies the relationships that are created in a learning context. Teamwork and collaboration are at the forefront of OL (Waite, 2011) and a key feature of LI development (Nasir and Cooks, 2009; Collett, 2020). Through OL, children work and learn alongside their peers in an environment outside the classroom. The outdoor environment allows children to express themselves in ways in which they may not be able to indoors. As children have the opportunity to express themselves differently outdoors, they may also make different connections with different peers in the outdoors.

Finally, the ‘when’ of LI development suggests that all the above must occur on a regular basis. It has been proven that longer or more regular OL interventions produced longer positive effects in participants while shorter or minimal OL produced less benefits which are soon lost by participants (O’Brien and Lomas, 2017; Harris, 2021).

To conclude, the benefits of OL align with the key competencies needed for LI development. Bernstein and Solomon's (1999) definition, what I am, where, with whom and when can be

naturally woven into OL in providing opportunity for LI development in primary school children.

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